

A Geographical Analysis on Land Use Pattern Changes in Minbya Township of Rakhine State

Min Min Aye Than*

Soe Thida**

Thinn Myat Khaing, Yin Yin Moe***

Abstract

This geographic study is an attempt to analysis the changes of land use patterns in Minbya Township of Rakhine State. The changes of land use types are obtained from Department of Agriculture and Land Records Department of Minbya Township. The study area has changed in patterns of land use (2003-04 – 2012-13) due to the pressure of growing population i.e. agricultural land, fuel and wood. The main objectives of this thesis are: (1) to observe the physical and human bases conditions in Minbya Township, (2) to evaluate the extent of land use patterns changes in Minbya Township, (3) to assess the causes and the impacts of land use pattern changes in Minbya Township. These statistics are verified by field observation and recorded on Geographic Information Systems. Then, spatial analysis is conducted by using ArcGIS Version 10 software. Based on analysis of derived data by using Microsoft Excel database, land use pattern changes are evaluated. It is found that the results the impacts on the land use in Minbya Township. Thus, integrated measures on the conservation of natural forest and other resources are essential in the future.

Introduction

Land is the basis need for many life support systems. Like any other natural resources, it is also limited. Land is becoming a scarce resource in many areas due to the pressure of growing population. This has led to an increasing need for systematic land use management.

Research Problems

Land use patterns changes are difference in spatial and temporal scale. According to this situation, this research presents to assessment the factors that controlling the changes land use in Minbya Township, to evaluate the impacts of land use.

Hypothesis

1. The characteristics and patterns of the natural environment cause the land use.
2. The human factors cause the land use pattern changes.
3. The land use changes impacted on the environment and socio- economy.

* Dr., Associate Professor, Department of Geography, Bago University

** Lecturer, Department of Geography, Dagon University

*** Assistance Lecturer, Department of Geography, Dagon University and Magwe University

Aim

This research aim to geographical analysis on the changes of land use patterns in Minbya Township of Rakhine State.

Research Design

In this research, part I analysed physical factors such as location, relief and drainage. Part II investigated human factors with growth of population, population distribution and population density. Part III concerns with current situation of land use conditions of the study area. Part IV were emphasized land use patterns changes of the office data from 2003-2004 to 2012-13. Part V, which conducted in causes and impacts of land use pattern changes. Suggestion and finding are discussed in part VI.

Sources of Data and Methodology

Land uses changes were examined from 2003-04 to 2012-13. Land use changes were analysed for the data acquired from offices and field survey. These collected data were analysed by statistical method and expressed by maps and diagrams combined with GIS (Geographic Information Systems).

I. Physical Factors of the Study Area

Location, Size and Boundaries

Minbya Township is located between 20° 5' N and 20° 55' N Latitude and 93° 6' E and 93° 52' E Longitude (Figure 1, 2 and 3). It respects to land and water because the study area lies between Rakhine Yoma on the east and the Bay of Bengal on the west. It has an area of 3466.6 square kilometers (1338.463 square miles or 856616 acres). It is 9.49 percent (3466.6 square kilometers) of the total area of Rakhine State (36519.04 square kilometers or 14100.08 square miles). It consists of 3 wards, 64 village tracts and 246 villages. It is bounded by on the

north by Chin State, east by Ann Township and Magway Region, on the south by Myebon Township, on the west by Pauktaw Township and Maruk-U Township on the northwest.

Figure 1 Location of Rakhine State within Myanmar

Figure 2 Location of Minbya Township in Rakhine State

Figure 3 Village Tracts of Minbya Township in Rakhine State

Source: Myanmar Survey Department

Relief and Drainage

It is divided into two types of relief such as the Eastern Mountain Ranges and the Western Alluvial Plain.

The Eastern Mountain area raises average height of 457.2 meters or 1500 feet. The prominent hill is Menhpu taung with 406.9 meters (1335 feet). It is the highest in the north and gradually lower in the south. There are few hills and low mountain range in the southern part of the study area. It is called the Kyatsin range and its average height is 304.8 meters (1000 feet).

The Western Alluvial Plain occupies half of the study area. It is a level flat land, which is a deltaic plain of Minkyaung, Kyatsin, Sun Ye rivers and Thinganet chaung. The height of the plain is about 15.24 meter (50 feet) above sea level. As these area has been built up by the Lemyo River and its tributaries crossing the study area. Therefore, the lowland creates fertile soils especially for paddy cultivation.

The main river is Lemyo River in the study area. It flows from north to south creating a deltaic condition. Panmyaung and Ta-ywe chaungs join into the Lemyo River on the east. Myaungbwe Chaung flows into the Lemyo River from the west. The lower part of Lemyo River is called Yamaung River still to Minbya Town. The mouth of river is known as Kyatsin River, it enter in Hunter's bay in Myebon Township. Other prominent tributaries are Yamaung River, Minkaung River, Pyunche and Thinganet chaungs. Sun Ye River is bounded by natural boundaries between Pauktaw and Minbya townships on the southwest. Generally drainage pattern of the study area is dendritic pattern.

II. Human Factors of the Study Area

Population Growth

Most of the people depend on the agricultural land use. The total population gradually increased in Minbya Township between 2003 and 2012. In 2003, total population accounted 101548 persons with growth of 1.2 percent. In 2012, the total population rapidly increased to 210826 persons and 1.0 percent in Table 1.

**Table 1 Total Population and Growth of Population
in Minbya Township (2003 -2012)**

Years	Total Population	(+/-)	Growth Rate (%)
2003	191548	-	
2004	193866	2318	1.2
2005	195978	2112	1.1
2006	198110	2132	1.1
2007	200131	2021	1.0
2008	202461	2330	1.2
2009	204624	2163	1.1
2010	206631	2007	1.0
2011	208718	2087	1.0
2012	210826	2108	1.0

Source: Immigration and Population Department in Minbya Township

Population Distribution and Density

Population distribution is influenced by physical features and economic conditions. Most of the eastern part of the study area is occupied by part of Rakhine Yoma. This part of the study area is covered with forest and consequently sparsely populated. A few people live in Oke Ta Rar (1065 person) and Kywe Tet (1192 persons) village tracts on the southwestern part of the study area. Yin Bway Village Tract settles 1201 persons on the southern part of the study area. Other sparsely populated area was found Thein Taung (1206 person) on the north. Distribution of population for the period 2012 showed uneven distribution of people in the study area. The highest population concentration was found in urban area (24345 persons) and six village tracts namely Na Ga Yar, Shwe Ta Mar, Pan Myaung, Thar Yar Kone, Ah Wa and San Bar Lay. These areas are located along the River, Road and the southern part of alluvium plain in Figure 4 and 5.

Figure 4 Distribution of Population in Minbya Township (2012-2013)

Figure 5 Density of population in Minbya Township (2012-2013)

Source: Immigration and Population Department in Minbya Township

III. Current Land Use Pattern Conditions

General Land Use

The study area is located between the Rakhine Yoma on the east and the Bay of Bengal on the west. Mountain ranges, hills and spurs cover about half of the township's area in the east. The general land use of Minbya Township is related to physical features, climate, underlying rocks, soils, natural vegetation and human beings.

The general land use of Minbya Township can be classified as follows:

- (1) Cultivated Land
- (2) Forest Land
- (3) Cultivable Waste Land
- (4) Uncultivable Land

The conditions of general land use types for 2012-13 was represented in Figure 6. The area of cultivated land consisted 38546 hectares (95249 acres) in 2012-13. It is third proportion of the study area. The largest land use pattern is uncultivated land of 183252.07 hectares present 452825 acres in 2012-13. Cultivable waste land is 10095.92 hectares (247342 acres) the second largest proportion of the township's area when compared with all other types of land use because it is a part of the Rakhine Yoma. Forests cover the last proportion of the township's area when compared with all other types of land use. It was 23999.11 hectares (59303 acres).

Figure 6. General Land Use Pattern of Minbya Township (2012-13)

Source: Land Records Department (Minbya Township)

Cultivated Land Use

Cultivated land use can be subdivided into le, ya, garden, dani and taungya lands. Of them, le occupied 33263 hectares or 86.29 percent and garden land 3100.71 hectares 8.04 percent of the total cultivated area of 38546 hectares. Other cultivated land use categories occupied less than 5 percent.

Figure 7. Pattern of Cultivated Land in Minbya Township (2012-13)

Source: Land Records Department (Minbya Township)

Forest

Forest land use is classified into reserved forest, unclassified forest and other forest. Other forest covers 23999.11 hectares (59303 acres) or 6.9 percent. It has five reserved forests (i) Bandula (1) Reserve Forest (ii) Bandula (2) Reserve Forest (iii) Bandula (3) Reserve Forest (iv) Bandula (4) Reserve Forest and (v) Bandula (5) Reserve Forest.

Cultivable Waste Land

All the waste land available for cultivation is included in the cultivable waste land and waste land. It requires the turning of their condition into productive land from cultivable waste land. The total area of cultivable waste land was 100095.92 hectares (247342 acres) or 28.87

percent in 2012-13. This type of land use is the second rank among all types of land use. It slightly changes from year to year.

Uncultivable Land

Uncultivable land use type includes with land use for factory, religious and cemetery, construction of road and dam, inn and land under water. Of them, underground water occupied about 4.50 percent and pasture land, religious and cemetery and other land use types share 2.60 percent, 1.86 percent and 89.5 percent respectively.

IV. Changes of Land Use Pattern

To analysis the land use change of study area, land records from 2003-04 to 2012-13 were used. Land use change was analysis both spatial and temporal dimensions. There are analysed by many methods of distribution map. Among them, four most common classification schemes are natural break, quartile, equal interval, and standard deviation. Natural break is good for mapping data that are not evenly distributed. Quartile method divides data into four classes. It is good for comparing areas that are roughly the same size.

Change of General Land Use

The total area of the township was 346660.8 hectares (856616 acres) within the 10-years of the study period between 2003-04 and 2012-13. In 2003-04, the cultivable land was 35068.50 hectares (86656 acres) or 10.12 percent of the total township's area. In 2012-13, the cultivated land increased to 39281.28 hectares (39281.28 acres) or 11.3 percent of the total township's area. The increase in cultivated land was mainly due to the increase of population and land reclamation from the cultivable waste land (Table 4.1).

During the period of 2003-04, the forest land was 26725.08 hectares or 7.71 percent and forest land remained with 23999.11 hectares (59303 acres) or 6.9 percent of total area of the township in 2012-13. Then, the area of forest land slightly varies from year to year. During the period between 2002-03 and 2012-13 forest area decreased was mainly due to exploitation of timber, firewood, and charcoal for the township and other townships and Ya cultivation on the marginal area increased.

In 2003-04, the cultivable waste land had high acreage, which was 103703.3 hectares (256256 acres) or 29.91 percent and 100095.9 hectares (247342 acres) or 28.87 percent of total area of the township in 2012-13. But the area of cultivable waste land slightly decreased during study time. This is mainly due to reclamation of cultivable lands.

During the period from 2003-04, the uncultivated land was 181163.9 hectares (447665 acres) or 52.26 percent and increased to 183248 hectares (452815 acres) or 52.86 percent of the total area of the township in 2012-13. It notably increased to 2084.1 hectares (504.34 acres) or 1.13 percent of the total area of the uncultivated land in 2012-13. This change is due to the extension of villages for human settlements (Figure 8).

Figure 8 General Land Use in Minbya Township (2002-03 to 2012-13)

Source: Land Records Department (Minbya Township)

Changes in Types of Agricultural Land Use

Changes in the type of agricultural land use depend on physical features of the study area. In Minbya Township the different types of agricultural land use can be classified as follows;

1. Le Land
2. Ya land
3. Garden Land
4. Dani Land
5. Taungya Land

Le Land

Le land is the most occupied type of agricultural land use practiced in Minbya Township. It is found in the low land and flat land with alluvial soils. Wet land is often designated as paddy land.

Figure 9 shows the distribution of le land in the study area from 2003-04 to 2012-13 and its change, respectively. The village tracts with high acreage gain is found particularly in the southwestern part of the township such as Khway Tauk Chaung, Aing Wan, La Har Kyay, Khaung Laung Chaung, Syun Ye and That Pone village tracts, which are located along the Syun Ye River. Village tracts which gained low high acreage are 51 village tracts most of the study area. The low acreage gain village tracts are found 5 village tracts in most of the regions margin of the forest area. There are Ywar Pyin, Bar Bu Taung, Min Ku Lan, Chaw Chaung and Yan Htaing village tracts. The study area is found unchanged area such as Kay Tha Lar Chaung Wa and Kay Tha Lar Pyun Wa village tracts.

Figure 9 Spatial Changes of Le Land (Percent) by Village Tract Area in Minbya Township (2003-04 and 2012-13)

Figure 9 Spatial Changes of Ya Land (Percent) by Village Tract Area in Minbya Township (2003-04 and 2012-13)

Ya Land

In 2003-04, 2012-13 and change distribution area of ya land show in Figure 10 in the study area. 24 village tracts with low high acreage gain are found particularly in the western part of the township. Most of the village tracts locate high land of the alluvium area. The low loss acreage gain of ya land was found 13 village tracts in the central region of the study area. Most of ya land area changed into garden land in the study area. Unchanged area is Kay Tha Lar Chung Wa and Kay Tha Lar Pyun Wa village tracts.

Garden Land

Garden land area changed into high low gain area was 54 village tracts. Ya land area converted into garden land area in the study area. The low loss acreage gain of garden land was found two village tracts such as urban and San Bar Lay Village Tract in the central region of the study area. Unchanged area is Kay Tha Lar Chung Wa and Kay Tha Lar Pyun Wa village tracts in Figure 11.

Dani Land

Dani land area changed into high low gain area was 32 village tracts. Dani land area along the stream and rivers in the study area. The low loss acreage gain of dani land extended 14 village tracts of the study area. Unchanged area of dani land was 18 village tracts because these village tracts were not found tidal action. In 2003-04, 2012-13 and change distribution present in Figure 12.

Figure 11 Spatial Changes of Garden Land (Percent) by Village Tract Area in Minbya Township (2003-04 and 2012-13)

Figure 12 Spatial Changes of Dani Land (Percent) by Village Tract Area in Minbya Township (2003-04 and 2012-13)

Taungya Land

Taungya land area was 8 village tracts these are Oe Pyin Taung, Htein Pin, Ku Lar Ma Taung, Done Gyi, Min Zi, Ngan Tet, Min Ku Lan and Kyaung Taung village tracts. Taungya land was started on 2005-06 in the study area. It was found near the high land area of the study area.

Changing Patterns of Agricultural Land Use

Agricultural patterns of Minbya Township include double cropping, mixed cropping and irrigated farming. The increase in total cultivated area is the result of the growing area of double, mixed and irrigated cropping.

The double cropping plays an important role in Minbya Township. The farmers grow the crops twice or more a year and obtain more income. Double cropped area depend on the State encouragement grow summer paddy from Myaung She in the study area. On the other hand, the double cropping area was the greatest with 15466.71 hectares (38219 acres) in 2012-13. In the study time from 2003-04 to 2012-13, the double cropped area was gradually increased in Table 2.

Table 2 Agricultural Pattern in Minbya Township (2003-04 to 2012-13)

Year	Double Crops (Hectare)	Mixed Crops (Hectare)	Irrigated Cropping (Hectare)
2003-04	4437.39	229.05	938.06
2004-05	12707.96	301.90	916.21
2005-06	13559.42	331.84	940.49
2006-07	14980.68	442.73	1039.23
2007-08	17573.50	527.31	1187.35
2008-09	17108.92	524.47	1344.37
2009-10	17630.97	523.26	1617.94
2010-11	18339.57	526.90	1846.18
2011-12	13746.38	530.54	1931.57
2012-13	15466.71	494.93	1940.88

Source: Land Records Department (Minbya Township)

In strip cropping pattern, not only a single crop but also many crops are grown altogether in the farm lands at the same time. If a previous crop failed because of unfavorable climatic conditions a second crop may be cultivated a little later. Mixed cropping area also increased from 229.05 hectares (566 acres) in 2003-04 to 530.54 hectares (1311 acres) in 2012-13 and decreased to 494.93 hectares (1223 acres) in the study area. It is the smallest area of the study area in Table 2.

In Table 2 shows irrigated cropping area increased from 938.06 hectares (2318 acres) in 2003-04 to 1940.88 hectares (4796 acres) in 2012-13 in the study area. It is mainly used in summer paddy and other crops such as chilly, aubergine, brinjal (egg plant) and mustard. It is second ranks of the cropping pattern in Minbya Township.

Cultivable Waste Land

All the waste lands available for cultivation is included in the cultivable waste land. It can be transformed into cultivated land, by effective use of financial investment and human resource. It was covered with trees, bushes and bamboo. The area under the cultivable waste land, it was gradually decreased from 2003-04 to 2012-13. In 2003-04, cultural waste land was 103703.3 hectares (256256 acres) which accounted 29.91 percent of township area, and was the second largest rank among all land use types.

In 2012-13, the acreages of cultivable waste land sharply decreased to 100095.9 hectares (247342 acres) which represented 28.27 percent of township area, and was the second largest area among all types of land use. It was not changed because it needed encouragement by the State to reclaim and the farmers themselves are interested to make more profit from agricultural activity.

In 2003-04, no cultivable waste land was 15 village tracts; Kin Seik, Ywar Pyin, Chaik Taung, Taung Poet Gyi, San Bar Lay, Na Yan, Pwint Htee, Than Shin, Sat Kyar, Ku Toet Seik, Win Zar, Kay Tha Lar Pyun Wa, Kay Tha Lar Chaung Wa, Hpa Laung Pyin and Sun Ye. There were the greatest cultivable waste lands in 9 village tracts with over 300 hectares (over

741 acres) and the smallest cultivable waste land in 35 village tracts with 1- 300 hectares (2.47 acres and 741 acres).

In 2012-13, there were no cultivable waste lands in 9 village tracts. There are Kin Seik , Ywar Pyin, Taung Poet Gyi, San Bar Lay, Sat Kyar, Kay Tha Lar Pyun Wa, Kay Tha Lar Chaung Wa, Hpa Laung Pyin and Sun Ye. Minbya Township was decreased to 9 village tracts, where the former waste lands were transformed into cultivated land. From 2003-04 to 2012-13, gained area was found in the south and eastern parts of the township area, reserved forest area and unreserved forest area. They converted to garden land.

The reduction of the waste land area has shifted to the cultivated land area. The gain of the waste land area was appears from the deforestation area. The high gain in the waste lands of this village tract was turned into plantation or garden crops.

Uncultivated Land

Uncultivated land includes land under settlements, land under water, pastoral land, transportation land and unclassified land. Uncultivated land, it was steadily increased from 2003-04 to 2012-13. In 2003-04, the area under uncultivable area was 181163.9 hectares (447665 acres) which represented 52.26 percent of the township area and it was first rank among all types of land use.

In 2012-13, the change of area of uncultivated land sharply increased to 183248 hectares (452815 acres) which showed 52.86 percent of township area and it was first rank. The sharply increase was accounted for by the extension of the areas settlement and cemetery and religious land.

In conclusion the general land use varied from 2003-04 to 2012-13. The forest land and cultivable waste lands notably changed into cultivated and uncultivable lands.

V. Causes and Impacts of Land Use Pattern Changes

Cause of Land Use Pattern Changes

Land use changes are connected with natural resource and human actions. The main factors of land use changes are relocation of the village settlements and reclamation of the waste land and decrease of forest area and increase of taungya cultivation.

Establishment of New Villages

Most of the populations are occupied with the agriculture. Growth of the population, all village tract but was separated by the study area in 2012-13 because rural land use pattern changes from 1272.74 hectares (3145 acres) to 1354 hectares (3345 acres) between 2003-04 and 2012-13. It was increased 6 percent of the settlement of the study area. It comprised 3 Wards, 62 village tracts and 246 villages in study time. So, establishment of new villages had either positive or negative effects from the changes of land use.

Reclamation of the Waste land

It can be transformed into cultivated land, by effective use of financial investment and human resource. It was covered with trees, bushes and bamboo. It was gradually decreased from 2003-04 to 2012-13 due to reclamation of the waste land. In 2012-13, the acreages of

cultivable waste land sharply decreased to 100095.9 hectares (247342 acres) which represented 28.27 percent of township area, and was the second largest area among all types of land use.

Decrease of Forest Area and Increase of Taungya Cultivation

The study area, forest area sharply decreased due to encroachment of agriculture and extraction of forest product. It significantly decreased to 24031.49 hectares (59383 acres) in 2012-13. Especially, it was found this situation eastern part of the study area because in this part near the settlement and unclassified forest area. Another cause, the study area was not found taungya cultivation in 2003-04. In 2005-06, it was found, 777.81 hectares (1922 acres) and it was increased to 1328 hectares (3281 acres) in 2012-13. The largest area of taungya cultivation was situated Min Ku Lan Village Tract with 950 hectares (2348 acres), which situated in eastern part of the study area especially near the forest area.

Impact of Land Use Pattern Changes

Deforestation

The reduced forest cover affects the general ecological environment causing drought, flood in the plain and flash flood in the mountain area (Asia Development Bank, 2001).

The main products of forest area are timber, bamboo, fire wood and charcoal as well as honey, resin and etc. Forests are necessary to regulate climate conditions, stream flow and reduce runoff, protect soil erosion, reduce the frequency and magnitude of flooding and serve as habitats for faunas and floras (RAP Publication, 2005).

Soil erosion takes place as forests are cut down and there remain no roots to hold the soils or the water. As a result, water in rivers, lakes and ponds were filled up with silt.

Population pressure causes a strong impact on land use change. Flood occurs because forests have been cleared or degraded, that direct links between deforestation and flood area. Virtually every flood related tragedy to men activities particularly to agricultural expansion, extension of taungya cultivation and timber extraction. Debate has been intense about how to prevent, mitigate and manage them.

All floods cannot be completely prevented. Flooding can maintain biodiversity, fish stocks and fertility of floodplain soils. In many floodplain crops such as paddy, pulses and groundnut, and other crops are cultivated.

VI. Findings and Suggestions

Findings

It is located between the Rakhine Yoma and Bay of Bengal. The study area enjoys tropical monsoon type (Am). A large water surplus experienced during the period from June to September. The vegetation types are supportive land use of the forest area which is source of timber. Total population was 191548 persons in 2003-04 and it increased to 210826 persons in 2012-13. Rural population was expanded more than urban population.

The changes of general land use pattern, this study area experienced the increase in paddy land, garden land, tungya land. It is especially due to the conversion of cultivatable waste land into le and ya lands and degraded forest land into taungya land. As a result, it encouraged the forest degradation and depletion.

Most of the people live in rural areas and their main economy of the study area was agriculture. The cultivated waste land was deducted and changed to cultivated land. In recent years degraded forest land was increased especially near the Min Ku Lan Village Tract in the eastern parts of the study area and near the reserved forest areas.

The crops are cultivated two times or three times in same farm area and the result was the increase use of chemical fertilizer and pesticides. Therefore, it has become one of the main causes for the destruction of soil formation and compounds in the long run period. This will tend to reduce the soil fertility resulting in reduced crop yields unless external nutrient inputs are supplied.

Suggestions

The main economy of the study area depends heavily on agricultural sector. However, least acreage was occupied by the cultivated land and the largest area was covered by forest land. For further development of the area the following points related to sustainable agricultural are suggested.

As agricultural production is only one of many farmer activities. Special emphasis is given to the possibilities of using the nutrients balance in cropping systems as an alternative to the measurement of soil fertility parameters.

Problems may be dealt with land improvement programs like agro-forestry and plantation development.

To minimize problems, reforestation activities it is necessary to do planned with minimal land development and will focus mainly on enrichment planting. Native species should be used for reforestation activities. Increased tree cover and proper design of plantations including land conservation measures may increase slope stability and reduce soil erosion.

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References

- Andy, M. (1999). *The ESRI guide to GIS analysis: volume 1, geographical pattern and relationship*. Environmental Systems Research Institute, Inc., Redlands, California.
- Asia Development Bank. (2001). *Integrated watershed management for land and water conservation and sustainable agricultural production in Asia*. Asia Proceeding of the ADB-ADB ICRISAT-IWMT Project Review and Planning Meeting (10-14 December 2001). Hanoi, Vietnam.
- Briassoulis, H. (2008). *Analysis of land use change: theoretical and modeling approaches*. the Web Book of Regional Science, <http://www.rrl.wvu.edu/WebBook/Briassoulis/contents.htm> (29-Jan-08 2:09:47 PM).
- Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO). (1995). *Planning for sustainable use of land resources*. FAO Land and Water Bulletin 2. Rome: Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations.
- Meyer, W.B. and B.L. Turner, II, eds. (1994). *Changes in land use and land cover: a global perspective*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.

- Meyer, W.B. and B.L. Turner, II. (1996). Land-Use/Land-Cover Change: Challenges for Geographers. *Geojournal* 39(3): 237-240.
- Ministry of Agriculture and Irrigation. (2004). *Soil type and characteristic of Myanmar*. Published by Ministry of Agriculture and Irrigation Department.
- RAP Publication. (2005). *Forest perspective 2: forest and flood*. Bangkok, Thailand.
- Skole, D.L. (1994). *Data on global land-cover change: acquisition, assessment, and analysis. In changes in land use and land cover: a global perspective*, eds. W.B. Meyer and B.L. Turner II, 437-471. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Turner, B.L. II, D. Skole, S. Sanderson, G. Fischer, L. Fresco, and R. Leemans. (1995). *Land-use and land-cover change; science/research plan*. IGBP Report No.35, HDP Report No.7. IGBP and HDP, Stockholm and Geneva.